

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: SEBABI****FIRST NAME: ONEN FRANCIS****PROGRAM CODE: DARM****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics*The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:*The author did use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 3%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. The term used to describe the usage of a source of information without giving credit to the original author:¹

- Referencing
- Source citing
- Plagiarism**
- Academic writing

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2. The term that describes a list containing all the items cited in academic writing²

- Citation

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fourth (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 34.

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² Cleenewerck and Gulma, 38.

- Bibliography**
 - Parenthesis
 - Quotation
3. The following are the building blocks when constructing an argument except:³
- Claim
 - Question
 - Evidence
 - Discouraging the doubters from questioning the evidence**
4. Which one of the following is the aim of conclusion in academic writing?⁴
- To leave readers with clarity of the claim
 - To facilitate understanding of the significance of the claim
 - To emphasize stating the claim in the later part of the conclusion**
 - To enhance mentioning the areas for future research
5. Which one of the following correctly describes a footnote?⁵
- Notes at the end of a page**
 - Notes at the end of a paragraph

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Thesis, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. Fitzgerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff, 9th Edition (London: The University of Chicago Press, Ltd., 2018), 60.

⁴ Turabian, 111.

⁵ Turabian, 148.

- Notes at the end of a chapter
- Notes at the beginning of a sentence

6. The following are acceptable practices in academic writing except:

- Paraphrasing someone written work
- Quoting someone written work
- Copying with the proper citing of the citation sources
- Stating someone's work without giving credit to the original author⁶**

7. Which one of the following statements is the most correct statement?

- Conceptual framework and theoretical framework are noted as synonymous
- Inductive research uses a conceptual framework
- Deductive research uses a theoretical framework
- The conceptual framework facilitates grounding and understanding of the propagation of knowledge⁷**

8. All the following are important in dissertation writing except:⁸

- Research title
- Plagiarism**
- Problem statement

⁶ Turabian, 139 & 140.

⁷ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from the Beginning to the End*, 4th ed. (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications Inc., 2019), 167.

⁸ Bloomberg and Volpe, page number.

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Purpose statement

9. In discouraging discriminatory connotation, the following should be avoided except:

Use of geographical connotations such as north, south, east, or west

Use of descriptions such as Western World

Use of salutations such as ‘Ms’ or ‘Mrs’ irrespective of the personal preference⁹

Respecting people association alongside convictions

10. The World Health Organization study guide recommends the following in the handling of numbers except:

Non-breaking spaces instead of commas

Combining numerals and words

A time of day should be written in 12 hours¹⁰

A date should be written as 11 May 2021 instead of 11/05/2021

⁹ WHO, *WHO Style Guide*, Second Edition, (WHO, 2013), 56.

¹⁰ WHO, 28.

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BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg and Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from the Beginning to the End*. 4th ed. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications Inc., 2019.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1, Fourth edition*. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

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Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Thesis, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. Fitzgerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. 9th Edition. London: The University of Chicago Press Ltd., 2018.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.